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Road traffic air pollution in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA), Lebanon – impact on public health: urgent need for public transport development, especially rail

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Abstract

Worldwide, more than 1.1 billion people live in urban areas that have an unhealthy air quality situation. While there are numerous sources of air-borne pollution, in most urban areas around the world, motorized road vehicles have become the single largest source of local air pollution – being responsible for nearly 50% of the emissions of smog precursors. In the Greater Beirut Area (GBA), Lebanon, there has not been a proper public transport infrastructure in place since the civil war (1975-1990). The resultant high dependency on private car use has led to significantly high levels of air pollution, which has a serious negative impact on public health. Public transport development, especially rail, is seen as a way to alleviate this problem, as well as to bring additional benefits to the country as a whole.

1. INTRODUCTION

Transport is fundamental for the social and economic development of countries, as well as for sustaining regional and global cooperation and economies. However, it is associated with a number of health-related issues, emanating from the increased levels of pollution (IPTEC, 2016).

With respect to Lebanon, a small country in the Middle East, studies show that it has the highest pollution-linked death rate, as a result of land transport (GREENPEACE MENA, 2020). According to a report titled "Toxic Air: The Price of Fossil Fuels", the estimated number of deaths in Lebanon attributable to fossil fuels was 2,700 in 2018 – a rate of four deaths per 10,000 people. The rate is one of the highest in the Middle East, alongside Egypt, which has a rate of three deaths per 10,000 people. The report, which is part of a campaign for the introduction of more renewable energy sources in the region, is particularly timely for highlighting the effect fossil fuel pollution has causing heart and lung diseases, and making residents more vulnerable to respiratory system viruses, such as coronavirus.

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Meanwhile, data from the report shows, fossil fuel-related pollution in Lebanon results in an extra 1.3 million days off work per year. While, economically, the effects of fossil fuel pollution reportedly swallow about two per cent of annual GDP, totaling approximately \$1.4 billion per year. In a country that is on the brink of an economic collapse, this cost [the \$1.4 billion] puts additional pressure on the finances of Lebanese citizens and their government and reveals an entirely new aspect of the economic crisis.

Noteworthy is that Lebanon is already in the midst of a debilitating economic crisis that has spiraled out of control since anti-government protests started in October 2019. The country is facing a severe dollar shortage and is seeking a bailout from the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the release of large international aid pledges to halt its economic collapse.

2. HIGH DEPENDENCY ON PRIVATE CAR USE LEADS TO AIR POLLUTION

Road transport in Lebanon consists of road-motorized vehicles only, since there is no appropriate infrastructure for non-motorized vehicles (e.g. bicycle lanes, safe storage space, convenient and affordable bike rentals). The road-motorized vehicle types consist of Passenger Cars (PC), Light-Duty Vehicles (LDV), Heavy-Duty Vehicles (HDV) and motorcycles (see Table 1).

Table 1. Description of the vehicle categories

Vehicle category	Description
Passenger Cars (PC)	Private personal gasoline cars used for mobility, including Sport Utility Vehicles (SUV).
Light Duty Vehicles (LDV)	Gasoline vehicles with rated gross weight less than 3,500 kg, including light trucks and coaches, designed for transportation of cargo or passengers.
Heavy Duty Vehicles (HDV)	Diesel vehicles with rated gross weight exceeding 3,500 kg, including heavy trucks and coaches, designed for transportation of cargo or passengers.
Motorcycles	Includes a mixture of 2-stroke and 4-stroke engines, as well as mopeds having an engine less than 50 cc.

The vehicle fleet distribution in Lebanon is shown in Figure 1. With 85%, passenger cars make up the majority of the total vehicle fleet.

Figure 1. The vehicle fleet distribution in Lebanon by vehicle type

Figure 2 reveals that the Lebanese vehicle fleet consists mainly of European vehicles.

Figure 2. The vehicle fleet in Lebanon by country of origin

The high dependency on private passenger car use has seriously exacerbated road traffic congestion in Lebanon, especially in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA), turning the daily commute to/from the city center of Beirut into an ordeal for many people (Choueiri, 2015).

The GBA, which extends from Nahr-el-Damour south of Beirut to Nahr-el-Kalb north of Beirut, see Figure 3, encompasses more than 40% of the population of Lebanon.

Figure 3. Map showing the main rivers in Lebanon

Furthermore, the occurrence of a high number of road traffic accidents in the GBA results in high inherent costs to the country's economy, and places a significant burden on public health (Choueiri, 2015).

2.1 Road Traffic Congestion

The World Bank estimates that some 650,000 motorised road vehicles enter the GBA daily (Rahhal, 2019). In a report published in 2015 (BLOMINVEST, 2015), it was noted that the number of daily motorised trips within the GBA, which has a population of over 2 million people, reached some 5 million, with about 68% of the journeys made by private car, and an occupancy rate of 1.6 persons/car. The high level of private car use not only results in serious road traffic congestion, especially during the peak-hour periods, but also has large financial consequences for the economy of Lebanon, as well as a very negative impact on the environment.

2.2 Environmental Impact

The high dependency on private car use not only causes serious road traffic congestion in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA), but also has a highly negative environmental impact as regards:

- *noise*: the road traffic congestion situation is accompanied with unacceptable levels of noise, due to the high traffic density, old vehicle engines, and also an excessive use of the claxon.

On the main roads of the Greater Beirut Area (GBA), noise levels reaching 90-95 dB have been measured, whereas the standard level is 72 dB. The measured noise levels fall into the category that is considered to cause irritation and may well also lead to health problems;

- *air pollution*: with 25% of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA) coming from the land transport sector, which is estimated to consume about 45% of all imported fuel, the contribution of road traffic to air pollution is very significant. The high levels of air pollution in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA), which has also become a serious deterrent to tourists to visit the city, lead to high medical costs due to illnesses caused by the said air pollution.

The contribution of the different vehicle categories to Greenhouse Gases (GHG) pollutants is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Contribution of the different vehicle categories to the indirect Greenhouse Gases (GHG) pollutants

Figure 4 (cont.). Contribution of the different vehicle categories to the indirect Greenhouse Gases (GHG) pollutants

Private Cars contribute to the highest share of emissions, with 58.38% of the total road transport emissions (CO₂-eq.), while Light-Duty Vehicles (LDV), Heavy-Duty Vehicles (HDV), and motorcycles account for 17.46%, 23.81% and 0.35%, respectively. Passenger cars are the main emitting subcategory of all GHG; Light-Duty Vehicles are the second most important contributor to CH₄; and Heavy-Duty Vehicles to CO and N₂O, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Contribution of the different vehicle categories to the GHG pollutants

2.2.1 Influx of Syrian Refugees – Exacerbation of Air Pollution

The road traffic congestion situation has also worsened over recent years, due to the influx of some 1.5 million refugees from neighboring Syria, who now make up roughly 25% of the resident population in Lebanon – this very large proportion is not only causing serious socio-economic problems, but is also putting a significant burden on public health in Lebanon – a country that has enough problems of its own, without having to deal with this disproportionate influx as well (see Table 2).

**Table 2. Number of displaced Syrians in Lebanon
EASC (EEA, 2014) and LCRP (Gol and UN, 2017)**

	Estimated Number of Displaced (EASC)	Estimated Number of Displaced (LCRP)
Displaced Syrians	1,730,000	1,500,000
Displaced Palestinians	55,000 (only Palestinian Returnees from Syria (PRS))	310,000 (including PRS & Palestinian Refugees in Lebanon (PRL))
Lebanese Returnees	50,000	35,000
Total	1,835,000	1,845,000

In 2014, the Lebanese Ministry of Environment (MoE), with support from the European Union (EU) and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), published the “Environmental Assessment of the Syrian Conflict & Priority Interventions (EASC)”, which provided an extensive analysis of the incremental environmental impact of the conflict in Syria. As regards air quality, EASC estimations state that, in 2014, the Syrian conflict resulted in an increase of up to 20% in the emission of air pollutants in Lebanon, which has resulted in a significant degradation of air quality (EEA, 2014).

While the findings of the assessment were based on an estimated number of displaced of some 1.8 million in 2014, the same estimation of the number of displaced was still applicable in 2017, and has been adopted by the Lebanese Government as part of the “Lebanon Crisis Response Plan (LCRP) for 2017-2020” (Gol and UN, 2017) – see also Table 2.

A return of the Syrians to their own country, when the situation allows again, would bring a great alleviation in the road traffic congestion situation in Lebanon, as well as in other respects. Their arrival has led to an increase in road traffic levels of about 15-25% with an inherent rise in the number of road traffic accidents, as well as air pollution, placing a not insignificant burden on public health.

2.3 Air Pollution

The main air pollutants resulting from motorized road vehicles are: carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrogen oxide (NO_x), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOC), suspended particulate matter (PM), ozone (O₃), carbon monoxide (CO) and lead (see also Fig. 2) (Waked et al., 2012).

Economic and environmental effects of road traffic air pollution include damage to buildings, food crops and forests. Identified health effects from road traffic air pollution include (see also Table 3):

- increased incidence of pulmonary diseases, such as asthma and emphysema;
- lung cancer, as well as cardiovascular diseases that can lead to heart attacks and strokes;
- mental retardation in children.

Table 3. Impact of main air pollutants on human health (EEA, 2014)

Pollutant	Health Impact
Particulate Matter (PM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can cause/aggravate cardiovascular and lung diseases, heart attacks and arrhythmias. • Can cause cancer. May lead to arteriosclerosis, adverse birth outcome and childhood respiratory diseases. The outcome can be premature death.

Table 3 (cont.). Impact of main air pollutants on human health (EEA, 2014)

Ozone (O ₃).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can decrease lung function. • Can aggravate asthma and other lung diseases. • Can lead to premature death.
Nitrogen Dioxide (NO ₂)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exposure to NO₂ is associated with increased all-cause, cardiovascular and respiratory mortality, and respiratory morbidity.
Sulphur Dioxide (SO ₂)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggravates asthma, and can reduce lung function and inflame the respiratory tract. • Can cause headache, general discomfort and anxiety.
Carbon Monoxide (CO)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can lead to heart disease and damage to the nerve system, as well as headache and fatigue.
Benzene (C ₆ H ₆)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is a human carcinogen – it can cause cancer.

3. ROAD TRAFFIC AIR POLLUTION: ITS IMPACT ON PUBLIC HEALTH IN BEIRUT

A study was conducted by the Ministry of Public Works & Transport (MoPWT) and the Ministry of Environment (MoE) that examined the socio-economic impact of road traffic air pollution on public health in Beirut, Lebanon. In this respect, it addressed the following issues:

- how serious an economic and social problem is road traffic air pollution?
- what impact does road traffic air pollution have on public health?
- what are the policy options available for mitigating road traffic air pollution?
- what are the economic benefits and costs of policy options for mitigating road traffic air pollution?

Within the framework of the study:

- measurements of ambient air quality were conducted at selected locations in Beirut;
- an inventory of health consequences was made, based hospital admissions and treatment surveys;
- ambient pollution concentrations over the city of Beirut were modelled.

3.1 Air-quality measurements: outcome

Based on the measurements of ambient air quality that were conducted at selected locations in Beirut, the levels of air pollutants present were estimated. In Table 4, a summary of the estimated levels of air pollutants in Beirut due to road vehicle emissions is shown, as well as the NAAQS (National Ambient Air Quality Standards) limits for Lebanon (it should be noted that the estimates should be regarded as best rough estimates of air pollutant concentrations in Beirut as, of course, actual readings cannot be made in all locations).

Table 4. Estimated levels of air pollutants due to road vehicle emissions in Beirut, and the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS) limits for Lebanon

Pollutant	Beirut Levels	NAAQS Limits
Particulate Matter (PM)	200 micro-g/m ³	50 micro-g/m ³ (annual average)

Table 4. Estimated levels of air pollutants due to road vehicle emissions in Beirut, and the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS) limits for Lebanon

Ozone (O ₃)	400 micro-g/m ³	235 micro-g/m ³ (annual average)
Nitrogen Dioxide (NO ₂)	12-100 micro-g/m ³ (linear model) 1,000 micro-g/m ³ (box model)	100 micro-g/m ³ (annual average)
Carbon Monoxide (CO)	30 mg/m ³ (box model)	10 mg/m ³ (8-hour average)
Lead	1.7-13.3 micro-g/m ³ (linear model) 14 micro-g/m ³ (box model)	1.5 micro-g/m ³ (quarterly average)

3.1.1 Particulate Matter (PM)

The sampling results for particulate matter (PM) indicate that there are dangerously high levels in Beirut. Although actual measurements for particulate matter (PM) are not available for all areas in Beirut, the study assumes that the average particulate matter (PM) concentration in the city of Beirut is 200 micro-g/m³. Experts in the field actually believe that this is a conservative value for the city as a whole.

3.1.2 Ozone

The average concentration of ozone in the city of Beirut is around 400 micro-g/m³. According to World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines, ozone concentration levels of between 400 and 500 micro-g/m³ are deemed unhealthy.

3.1.3 Nitrogen Dioxide, Carbon Monoxide and Lead

The modelling results for nitrogen dioxide, carbon monoxide and lead yield average concentration levels in Beirut that are all higher than prescribed by international standards.

3.2 The Impact of Particulate Matter (PM) on Public Health

In the following, the impact of the high levels of particulate matter (PM) in Beirut as regards estimated mortality, estimated excess mortality, estimated mortality costs, as well as hospital admissions is addressed.

As can be deduced from reviewed studies, an increase of 10 micro-g/m³ in particulate matter (PM) is associated with:

- an increase of 1% in the rate of mortality;
- an increase of 2% in the total number of hospital admissions;
- an increase of 2% in hospital respiratory and cardiovascular admissions;
- an increase of 2% in emergency hospital visits for respiratory diseases.

3.2.1 Estimated Mortality

The estimated annual mortality rate in Lebanon stands at 8.2 deaths per 1,000 inhabitants, as deduced from national surveys. Without the Syrian, Palestinian and other refugees, the population of Lebanon

totals about 4 million, of which one-third lives in the capital Beirut and its suburbs. It then follows that the estimated number of deaths per annum is some 33,000 in all of Lebanon, of which 11,000 in Beirut.

3.2.2 Estimated Excess Mortality

Excess mortality refers to the increase in the number of deaths that occurs as a result of a certain increase in air pollution levels. The study found that an increase of 10 micro-g/m³ in particulate matter (PM) concentration results in an increase of 1% in the rate of mortality. Consequently, a 10 micro-g/m³ increase in particulate matter (PM) concentration is estimated to result in 110 excess deaths in Beirut. If a 1% increase in mortality rate (110 deaths) is associated with a 10 micro-g/m³ increase in particulate matter (PM), then the estimated particulate matter (PM) concentration of 200 micro-g/m³ due to road vehicle emissions in the city of Beirut, noted in Table 3, accounts for an estimated 2,200 (110 x 20) excess deaths per annum.

3.2.3 Estimated Excess Mortality Cost

Considering the lowest possible value of social life (VOSL) estimate of USD 600,000 per person in the USA, the VOSL for Lebanon, after adjusting it for the income differentials between the two countries, would be a very conservative USD 59,155 per individual. The VOSL of USD 59,155 is used in the analysis as an estimate of the average excess mortality cost (N.B.: VOSL varies with income, age, gender, as well as level of education. A VOSL of USD 59,155 is higher than the amount a judge would award as compensation for accident victims in Lebanon. The average compensation to the families of accident victims ranges from USD 20,000 to USD 50,000, depending on various socio-economic factors).

3.2.4 Hospital Admissions

The annual number of hospital admissions in Lebanon is estimated at 455,000. It is estimated that about one-third of these, or 150,000, take place in Beirut. Further:

- the average daily cost of hospitalization, for all diseases, is estimated at USD 495.29 (+/- USD 3.81 at the 95% confidence level). The average duration of hospitalization is estimated at 3.32 days (+/- 0.0376 days at the 95% confidence level). The estimated cost noted is based on the mean bill for approx. 49,000 cases of hospital admissions for various diseases;
- the average duration of hospitalization is used to estimate the average number of impaired economic activity days per individual which, for all diseases, is conservatively estimated to stand at 498,000 (i.e. 150,000 x 3.32) days in Beirut;
- the average daily wage is estimated to be approx. USD 34.00, when assuming 22 working days per month. Consequently, the total cost of impaired economic activity days for Beirut, due to hospitalization, for all diseases, is estimated at approx. USD 16,932,000 (498,000 days x USD 34.00);
- the proportion of admissions involving respiratory and cardiovascular ailments in Beirut is estimated to represent approx. 15% of the total number of hospital admissions. This is equivalent to 22,500 (i.e. 150,000 x 0.15) admissions, of which respiratory ailments represent around 37%, or 8,325 admissions. Whereas cardiovascular ailments make up the balance with 63%, or 14,175 admissions.

The aforementioned clearly shows that road traffic air pollution has a significant impact on public health in Beirut, and that measures to reduce air pollution levels are urgently needed.

4. AN EFFICIENT AND MODERN PUBLIC TRANSPORT SYSTEM: THE SOLUTION

Mitigating the impact of road traffic air pollution on public health in Beirut requires:

- reducing exhaust-gas emission levels of all motorised road vehicles by means of technical interventions at the stage of production or retrofitting;
- encouraging people to use transport modes that have a less harmful environmental impact;
- reducing overall motorised road vehicle use.

Minimizing road traffic congestion and reducing the number of motorized road vehicles operating on the roads would be one aspect of reducing road traffic air pollution and its impact on public health. By improving road traffic flows and circulation, and providing facilities and an improved road infrastructure could alleviate some of the problem. Improving access to and mobility within the city center of Beirut, as well as enhancing the pedestrian environment and, at the same time, relieving the adverse impact of the high level of private car use are only a few examples of how the road traffic situation could be somewhat improved – but not enough.

Building more roads, demolishing buildings to make space for more cars, and adding more parking spaces will only exacerbate the problem. In a report for a road traffic congestion situation in the United Kingdom (Leigh, 2016), it is noted that such measures would only provide a temporary relief until the induced demand replenishes the space available on the roads, and also that business cases to solve road traffic congestion should be developed very carefully and take into account the prevailing situation in the specific city and country in question.

In the case of Beirut, decreasing road traffic congestion by developing more roads, for instance, is not a viable option because of its urban density and terrain, with the mountains to one side, the sea to another, and a narrow coastal strip in-between. Any road development project would require either the expropriation of land or the construction of tunnels in mountains or that of highways over the sea, all of which would be costly options. This leaves the development of an efficient and modern public transport system as the only and most favorable option, as implementation of such a system would achieve:

- a reduction in road traffic air pollution;
- a reduction in road traffic congestion;
- a reduction in expenditure on road infrastructure expansion;
- a reduction in road traffic accident rates; and
- a reduction in fuel consumption.

Foremost, because of the reduced road traffic accident rates, as well as the reduced road traffic air pollution it would bring, the implementation of an efficient and modern public transport system would significantly alleviate the very dire public health situation in Beirut.

4.1 An Efficient and Modern Public Transport System (Choueiri, 2014; Choueiri, 2018; Choueiri, 2020)

Studies to implement an efficient and modern public transport system to alleviate road traffic congestion in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA) are underway. Among these studies, also railways are looked at. In this respect, a number of routes are under focus for possible revitalization, including (see also Figure 6):

Figure 6. Routes are under focus for possible revitalization

- *Beirut - Jounieh - Tabarja-Maameltein (- Tripoli)*: in an effort to alleviate road traffic congestion in Beirut, especially on the northern approach into the city centre, studies have been conducted to see if the situation could be alleviated by implementing railway services between Beirut and Tabarja-Maameltein, and even beyond to Tripoli, using the existing coastal railway right-of-way. If sufficient funds were to become available, it has been recommended to extend the studies also to south of Beirut, at least to the coastal town of Jiyeh, near Sidon;
- *Tripoli - Abboudiyeh*: the government has assigned the Council for Development and Reconstruction (CDR) of Lebanon to look into the possibility of revitalising the railway line between Tripoli and Abboudiyeh on the Lebanese/Syrian border, in coordination with the country's Railways & Public Transport Authority (RPTA);
- *SkyWay*: another option that could be considered is to implement not a ground-borne railway system, but an elevated SkyWay system between Rafik Hariri International Airport (Beirut) and Casino du Liban (Jounieh) with intermediate stations at key locations. Such a system could alleviate the serious road traffic congestion situation near the airport and, thus, provide an efficient and reliable transport alternative for people traveling to/from the airport, as well as other destinations served by this route.

For the aforementioned railway lines to become a reality, it would take quite some time. However, the dire road traffic congestion situation needs to be alleviated much sooner – a temporary solution could come in the form of the Greater Beirut Urban Transport (GBUT) project.

4.1.1 The Greater Beirut Urban Transport (GBUT) Project

The Greater Beirut Urban Transport (GBUT) project, by implementing a new Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) system between the densely-populated Tabarja-Maameltein/Jounieh area and Beirut, as well as feeder bus services to the trunk BRT system and within Beirut, is aimed at improving transport connectivity and mobility on the northern approach into the city centre of Beirut.

The GBUT project also includes the establishment of appropriate institutional entities for the management, operation and maintenance of this BRT system. Once effected, it would become Lebanon's first modern public transport system in decades.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Lebanon is currently facing a wide array of problems, the worst since the civil war (1975-1990). Besides having to deal with the currently prevailing corona virus (Covid-19) pandemic, the country is faced by a socio-economic, financial, political, health, and humanitarian crisis, as well as the aftermath of the large-scale explosion that occurred at the Port of Beirut on 4 August 2020, which not only shook the buildings in Beirut, but also the people of this city and the country as a whole.

Since the civil war, there has not been an efficient public transport infrastructure in place in Lebanon due to a lack of funds and, therefore, there is a high dependency on private car use. This high dependency on private car use has seriously exacerbated road traffic congestion in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA), resulting in a significant increase in road traffic air pollution and accidents, which has a significant negative impact on public health.

The development of an efficient and modern public transport system with optimal services and facilities, once in place, could greatly alleviate road traffic congestion, as well as reduce road traffic air pollution and road traffic accident rates in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA) – this would enhance the health and quality of life of the people and, thus, alleviate the high burden placed on public health.

However, for all this to become a reality, the financial support from external bodies (e.g. World Bank, the European Union (EU), the European Investment Bank (EIB) and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)) would be very much needed.

In closing, it should be borne in mind that reducing the exhaust-gas emissions from road traffic – by implementing an efficient and modern (rail) public transport system – would not only benefit the health of the citizens of Beirut and Lebanon as a whole, but also the sustainability of the global climate we all live in and depend upon – as also the Covid-19 pandemic has shown, we all breathe the same air!

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